

CERTIFICATE

of publication

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MULTIDISCIPLINARY SCIENCE

Kasimova Odina Alimjonovna

for publication of paper entitled

**THEME: O'ZBEKISTONDA AKADEMIK MOBILLIK – ZAMONAVIY
TA'LIM TIZIMINING AJRALMAS QISMI**

13.12.2025

DATA

Dr. Rajeet Ojha
Editor in chef

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